

ESSENTIAL COMMENTS ON THE CHARACTERISTICS DUE TO THE ORIGIN OF CLINICAL TERMS AND FEATURES OF CLINICAL TERMINOLOGY

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Abstract: This article discusses the characteristics of Latin clinical terms. It provides information on the formation and interconnection of clinical terms, the place and role of prefixes and suffixes in the formation of terms.

Keywords: clinic, pneumonia, treatment, terms, pathological condition, Mythological, prefixes, suffixes

СУЩЕСТВЕННЫЕ ЗАМЕЧАНИЯ ПО ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКАМ, ОБУСЛОВЛЕННЫМ ПРОИСХОЖДЕНИЕМ КЛИНИЧЕСКИХ ТЕРМИНОВ И ОСОБЕННОСТЯМИ КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ ТЕРМИНОЛОГИИ

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются характеристики латинских клинических терминов. Приводятся сведения об образовании и взаимосвязи клинических терминов, месте и роли приставок и суффиксов в образовании терминов.

Ключевые слова: клиника, пневмония, черта, термины, патологическое состояние, мифологическое, приставки, суффиксы.

INTRODUCTION

The word "clini", from which the words "clinic", "clinical", Greek, it means "bed, bed of the sick." Clinical terminology includes terminological names of diseases and pathological conditions, methods of treatment and examination of patients, names of medical instruments.

If in anatomical terminology most of the terms are of Latin origin, then in clinical terminology there is a large number of words and morphemes of Greek origin. This is due historically: firstly, by the fact that the literature concerning diseases and their treatment was mainly translated by the Romans from the Greek language, and secondly, by the fact that most of the doctors who practiced in Rome were Greeks. The great flexibility of the Greek language in relation to the formation of new terms, in comparison with Latin, cannot be discounted.

Clinical terminology began to take shape in the era of Hippocrates. Many clinical terms are associated with the name of this famous doctor, for example, facies Hippocratica "Hippocratic mask" (the face of a dying person).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Some terms of clinical terminology have developed historically as metaphors, i.e. words used in a figurative sense. So, the term cancer (cancer) was associated with some external similarity between a cancerous tumor of the breast and the contour of a crayfish. The terms pectus carinatum "chicken breast, rachitic chest" (from Latin pectus "breast" and carina "protrusion of the chest in birds like a keel"), hordeolum "barley on the eyelid" (diminutive of the Latin hordeum "barley") and etc.

A special group is made up of terms formed on the basis of associations with mythological images. Mythological ancient images and plots formed the basis of many outstanding works of literature, painting, and architecture. Mythological images are also widely represented in the terminological systems of many sciences, especially the humanities. In medicine, mythological images underlie such terms as lethargic sleep (Leta is the river of oblivion), cyclopia "cyclopia, one-eyedness" (Cyclops is a mythical giant with one round eye. In clinical medicine, this is a

congenital deformity of development, leading to one-eyed fetus). Many terms of clinical psychiatry also go back to ancient Greek myths: the Oedipus complex, the Jocasta complex, the Electra complex, the Medea complex, etc.

The foundation is one of the productive ways of term formation. In Latin, the basic structure was not very common, but in Greek it is a very common model of word formation. In modern medical terminology, there are terms formed by the addition of both Latin and Greek bases, as well as mixed Latin-Greek formations.

Word stems can be connected with the connecting vowels -o- and -i-, as well as without the use of a connecting vowel. When connecting two or more Greek stems, the connecting vowel -o- is usually used, and when connecting Latin stems, the vowel -i- is used.

It should be remembered that the same Greek stem can be conveyed in different ways by means of the Latin language. (Example: cheir- and chir- "hand", kephal- and cephal- "head".)

In clinical terminology, the following Greek terminology elements are used, denoting teaching, science, method of diagnostic examination, treatment, suffering, illness: -logia (logos) - science, division of science; -logo- - related to speech disorders; -scopia (scopeo) - inspection with instruments, observation, research; -metria, -metr- (metreo) - measurement, determination of size, magnitude; -graphia (grapho) - the process of recording an image, graphic recording of signals; -gramma (gramma) – result of recording, registration of signals; -therapia (therapeia) - non-surgical treatment; noso- (nosos) - disease; patho-, -pathia (pathos) - 1) suffering, illness; 2) mood; alg-, -algia, -algesia (algos) - painful sensitivity, pain; -odynia (odyne) - pain.

Word stems that come from different languages but have the same meaning are called doublets. In medical terminology, there are a large number of Greco-Latin doublets (for example, vertebra - vertebra (Lat.) and spondyl- (Greek)). Latin doublets are used mostly in anatomy, while Greek doublets are used in clinical medicine.

Some terms of clinical terminology go back to borrowed words of the third Greek declension. III declension in Greek, as well as in Latin, was characterized by the fact that the bases of I. p. and oblique cases were different. This difference lies in the lengthening of the stem: the stem of R. p. and other oblique cases, as a rule, is longer than the stem of I. p. For example, in I. p. the Greek word for "body" has the form soma (stem som-), and in P n. - somatos (base somat-). Similarly, the Greek word for "mouth" has the form stoma (stem stom-) in I. p. and stomatos (stem stomat-) in R. p. The third declension in Greek includes nouns of all three genders, as well as some adjectives. Adjectives of the III Greek declension, as well as nouns, have different stems of I. p. and oblique cases. For example, the Greek adjective of the III declension pan "all, everyone" in R. p. has the form pantos.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

When forming complex clinical terms from the stems of words of the III declension, the stem of indirect cases is usually used, but sometimes the stem of I. p. is also taken. For example, terms such as somatometry (a set of methods for determining body size and weight), somatotype (type of body structure, physique), are formed from the basis of R. p. of the noun soma, and somatropin (growth hormone) - from the basis of I. p.

Term elements denoting pathological changes in organs and tissues, therapeutic and surgical techniques:

- clasia - a surgical operation to destroy an organ, part of the body;
- ectomia - surgical removal, excision of an organ, tissue;
- ectasia - stretching, expansion of a tubular or hollow organ;

- eurisis - expansion of the organ;
- iatria - healing, treatment;
- lysis - dissolution, destruction, resorption, melting; dissection of adhesions, adhesions, scars;
- malacia - softness, abnormal softness;
- pexia - a surgical operation of attachment, fixation of any internal organ;
- plastica - a surgical operation to restore an organ;
- ptosis - prolapse of an organ;
- rhapsia - surgical operation of suturing;
- schisis - splitting of the organ;
- sclerosis - compaction, hardening;
- stenosis - narrowing;
- stomia - a surgical operation of imposing an artificial opening, fistula, anastomosis (between organs, vessels);
- tomia - a surgical operation of dissection, opening.

Some clinical terms do not originate from Greek or Latin words, but go back to other languages. For example, the term pneumonia crouposa (there is also a variant of cruposa) is "croupous pneumonia". This term was introduced by the famous Russian doctor and researcher Sergei Petrovich Botkin to refer to the severe course of lobar pneumonia. The term comes from the English croup "croak" and indicates the characteristic "croaking", "barking" cough and hoarse voice in croupous pneumonia.

There are also terms-eponyms, that is, named after a particular scientist. For example, in clinical terminology, the term Tourette's syndrome is used (a combination of tic-like twitches of the muscles of the face, neck and shoulder girdle, involuntary movements of the lips and tongue with frequent coughing, spitting and coprolalia). This term goes back to the name of the French neurologist Gilles de la Tourette. Eponymous terms are quite numerous in clinical medicine: Marfan's syndrome (a disease from the group of hereditary connective tissue pathologies), Gilbert's syndrome (a common form of hereditary pigmentary hepatosis), Asperger's syndrome (one of the developmental disorders, characterized by serious difficulties in social interaction, as well as limited stereotyped, repetitive repertoire of interests and activities), ankylosing spondylitis (a systemic chronic inflammatory disease of the joints and spine), Parkinson's disease (a slowly progressive chronic neurological disease characteristic of older people) and many others.

In terms of structure, clinical terms can be divided into three large groups.

Firstly, these are terms consisting of one word, simple in word-formation structure, i.e., consisting of a root and an ending.

Secondly, these are derivative words formed by the prefix, suffix, prefix-suffix method or the method of adding roots (bases). Such clinical terms have a structure that allows you to give a detailed description of the phenomenon. For

example, diseases that are inflammatory in nature are designated by a term that is compiled on the basis of the anatomical name of the affected organ and the term element -itis, indicating an inflammatory process, for example, osteomyelitis "inflammation of the bone marrow", lymphadenitis "inflammation of the lymph node".

If the inflammatory process affects the outer shell of the organ, then the term receives the prefix peri- "about, around" - perinephritis "inflammation of the fibrous capsule of the kidney." If the process affects the inner lining of the organ, the term gets the prefix endo- "inside" -

endocarditis "inflammation of the inner lining of the heart." If the inflammatory process covered the tissues around the organ, the term received the prefix para- "near, next to" - paraproctitis "inflammation of the tissue surrounding the rectum".

The third group of clinical terms is phrases (for example, pneumonia crouposa - croupous pneumonia, pneumonia apicalis - apical pneumonia). Each phrase has a defined word - a noun in I. p. hours or more h. Defining words are, as a rule, adjectives. Their role is to clarify in a certain respect a generic (general) concept. The most common meaning of defining words is the localization of the lesion: abscessus appendicis, abscessus femoris, abscessus parietis arteriae, etc.

CONCLUSIONS

The number of terms related to the field of clinical terminology is very large, and it is almost impossible to master them through simple memorization. But since most clinical terms are complex in composition and consist of simpler elements, then, knowing the meaning of these elements (roots, stems, prefixes, suffixes), it is much easier to master the necessary amount of terminology.

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